

Accessory Pathway: Intermittent Conduction!

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Description

The above electrocardiogram (ECG) was obtained in a young patient with infrequent palpitations. The rhythm reveals sinus rhythm at 96 beats per minute. Normally conducted QRS complexes are followed by broader QRS complexes with short PR interval and slurring indicative of delta waves due to ventricular preexcitation, in a 2:1 manner.

Discussion

Wolfe-Parkinson-White (WPW) syndrome describes the occurrence of an arrhythmia related to the presence of an accessory pathway (bypass tract), and has been reported in approximately 0.1% – 0.3% of the general population [1]. The presence of a bypass tract can be an incidental finding on an ECG, or diagnosed as a result of symptoms ranging from palpitations, dizziness, syncope or sudden cardiac death.

Risk stratification of a bypass tract may require an electrophysiology study. The intermittent

conduction across an accessory pathway, as in the above ECG, or the loss of conduction during exercise, at higher heart rates [2], have often been taken as a sign of a weakly-conducting benign pathway. This, however, may not apply to all cases, and proceeding with electrophysiological (EP) evaluation, despite an intermittently conducting pathway, is recommended in symptomatic patient [3].

Medical management and watchful waiting may be prudent in asymptomatic patients with ECG features of a benign pathway. However, in symptomatic patients, or asymptomatic patients with ECG features portending high risk for an arrhythmia, EP ablation is recommended [4].

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